

Modern Immunopathological Changes and Views of Vitiligo

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Annotation: This article covers the results of today's advances in science about the role of immunological processes, which are important in vitiligo. Investigations conducted on the identification of cellular and tissue hormones - cytokines, which participate as promoters of melanocyte apoptosis or suppressing its activity in the tissue, are studied. The collected data serve as the main source of information important in the study of the etiopathogenesis of the disease.

Keywords: vitiligo, apoptosis, immunopathogenesis, cytokine, oxidative stress.

Introduction. Vitiligo is an acquired, multifactorial complex depigmented skin disease characterized by the formation of white-milky patches due to dysfunction of melanocytes in the epidermis. (3,4,20) Vitiligo is caused by a multifactorial etiological factor, which is caused by genetic and non-genetic factors. Our scientific knowledge is mainly based on autoimmune, oxidative stress, genetic and neurochemical hypotheses. Melanocyte destruction in vitiligo lesions is directly related to the proliferation of antimelanocyte bodies, the imbalance and dysfunction of T-lymphocytes (CD4+/CD8+ and IL). (10, 11,21)

A pathogenetic feature of vitiligo that needs to be studied is the loss of melanocytes. This disease, in turn, affects the quality of life of the patient by causing skin depigmentation. Several theories have been proposed to explain the pathogenesis of the disease, taking into account the role of increased inflammation and cytotoxic immune responses, neuropeptides, microvascular abnormalities, intrinsic abnormalities in the function of melanocytes and keratinocytes, as well as oxidative stress (2,29,30).

In recent decades, clinical, basic and translational studies on patient analyses, as well as in vitro and in vivo models, have significantly improved our understanding of the pathophysiology of the disease and revealed its complexity. Such progress is essential for identifying appropriate therapeutic targets and treatments to halt disease progression and promote repigmentation. (2,6,10)

Melanocyte loss in vitiligo is associated with persistent T-lymphocyte infiltration. The causes leading to infiltration may also be important, including environmental factors, genetic polymorphisms, metabolic changes, and autoimmune processes. In general, the stress response of epidermal cells to stress by overproduction of inflammatory mediators triggers the innate immune system, which in turn leads to melanocyte loss in vitiligo through the activation of autoimmunity. Receptors for the recognition of damaged genetic information by the innate immune system are involved in the inflammatory-autoimmune state. (5,7,33,34)

Clinical, experimental, and basic research conducted over the past decade have significantly improved the understanding of the pathophysiology of vitiligo and have led to new therapeutic insights. As a result, prospects for effective treatment of the disease are emerging. The fact that vitiligo is a complex disease with several components, including environmental factors, leaves the need to study the hidden problem in melanocytes. Such components may include triggers, genetic predisposition, increased oxidative stress, and abnormal immune and inflammatory processes. Vitiligo is characterized by the loss of epidermal melanocytes, although several cells are affected by immune and non-immune changes. (1,9,12,13)

Genetic studies have revealed that the **308 G/α gene polymorphism** in the promoter gene is directly related to an increased level of the cytokine TNF-α in the blood and may be a risk factor for the development of this disease. (Wu et al., 2015) In the study of gene polymorphisms in the pathogenesis of vitiligo (Saatov B.T. 2016), several pathological alleles were also identified in patients with vitiligo,

including the rs1800629 TNF- α gene polymorphism. This gene is characterized by a variety of alleles and genotypes in healthy people and vitiligo patients. It was found that the frequency of the random allele polymorphism in the TNF- α gene in patients with vitiligo is 2.2 times higher. In vitiligo, the carriage of the allele gene in the rs1800629 TNF- α polymorphism may contribute significantly to the risk of developing vitiligo.

Autoimmune diseases have long been considered as disorders of the natural immune process, and vitiligo is no exception. There is evidence of genetic and transcriptome modulation and accumulation of cellular immunity genes in vitiligo skin and blood analyses. The activation of PAMPs and DAMPs acts as a bridge between innate immune mechanisms and the activation of stress, the Koebner phenomenon, infections, or secondary acquired immune responses. This information is important for the correct approach to treatment and prevention of primary and secondary disease.

NK cells. NK cells are described as a bridge between innate and adaptive. They are characterized by early and potent production of IFN γ . As discussed above, they are transcriptional information. The supporting role of innate immunity in vitiligo is primarily based on differential gene expression associated with NK cell function, activity, and cytotoxicity (10, 11). It has been known for almost 30 years that an increase in circulating NK cells is observed in the blood of vitiligo patients with abnormalities in their expression of the CD158a inhibitory receptor and their activity (26, 27,13), but their role in vitiligo skin was not studied until recently. They confirmed an increase in the number of cytotoxic NK cells not only in the blood but also in the skin of vitiligo patients compared with healthy controls, mainly in unaffected skin (37,8,9). In addition, vitiligo NK cells are more sensitive to stress, produce higher amounts of IFN γ after stress, and are directly involved in the initiation of long-term adaptive immunity against melanocytes. Innate lymphoid cells. Innate lymphoid cells (ILK) secrete IFN γ in response to the vitiligo cytokines IL-12, IL-15, and IL-18. We have recently shown that ILC1 (but not ILC2 or ILC3) are increased in blood and skin in vitiligo and that these cells are the primary source of IFN γ , which is involved in early melanocyte apoptosis and subsequent T-cell-mediated melanocyte destruction. (6,18,19) The innate immune system, which is triggered by epidermal cells in response to stress, leads to the loss of melanocytes in vitiligo through an autoreactive immune response. Epidermal cells, melanocytes, and Langerhans cells are classified as dendritic cells. The principal antigen-presenting cells (APCs) are dermal dendritic cells, which are closely associated with Langerhans cells. APCs internalize foreign antigens by endocytosis and phagocytosis and produce antigenic peptides. After APCs bind the glycoprotein, they convert to MHC class II and form a complex with the foreign antigen protein, forming a T lymphocyte antigen. During this process, melanocytes bypass the primary APCs and bind to MHC class II through IFN γ stimulation (15,16,17). Phagocytosis also occurs in melanocytes. According to Le Poole et al., melanocytes can phagocytose, which was tested on 1 μ m latex and identified keratinocytes. (18,11,12) Le Poole et al. reported that melanocytes have the ability to process antigen and present phagocytosed antigen as target cells of T lymphocytes (15). Melanocytes participate in the adaptive immune system by expressing intercellular adhesion factor ICAM-1 at cell-cell junctions in the immune system, such as dendritic cells and CD40. (17,19,20,21) Melanocytes, along with APCs, activate the immune response by producing the cytokines IL-1 α , IL-1 β , IL-8, and TGF- β 1 (22,23,24). These findings suggest a role for melanocytes as antigen-presenting cells.

Melanocytes have also been proposed as **immunocompetent cells** capable of antigen processing, co-stimulating tissue hormones and IFN γ , which subsequently stimulate cytotoxic T lymphocytes through direct stimulation (7,11,28,35). The B-isoform (CXCR3B) of melanocytes has recently been shown to upregulate chemokine receptors and melanocytes at the site of injury, and these receptors play an important role in anti-melanocyte immunity. Recent studies have shown that there is a close relationship between the innate immune response and melanocyte function. pDCs, NK cells, and ILC1 enhance the activity of antigen-presenting melanocytes, which is essential for disease initiation, making these cells ideal primary targets for therapeutic intervention. **Melanocyte loss is a pathogenetic hallmark of vitiligo.**

Progressive depigmentation of the skin has a significant negative impact on the quality of life of patients. To date, vitiligo remains a therapeutic challenge. Several theories have been proposed to explain the pathogenesis of the disease, including the role of increased inflammatory and cytotoxic immune responses, neuropeptides, microvascular abnormalities, intrinsic abnormalities in melanocyte and keratinocyte adhesion, and oxidative stress (2,11,12,26,31,32). In recent decades, clinical, basic, and translational studies in patient samples as well as in vitro and in vivo models have significantly improved our understanding of the pathophysiology of the disease and highlighted its complexity. Such progress is essential for identifying appropriate therapeutic targets and treatments to halt disease progression and induce repigmentation. “Vitiligo immunology” focuses on additional aspects of the immune pathways involved in vitiligo from a pathophysiological perspective. Mechanisms leading to melanocyte loss include genetic predisposition and environmental triggers, as well as metabolic and immune alterations (3,4,31,24). Epigenetic modifications may also be involved in the pathogenesis of vitiligo, as suggested by Pu et al. This study identifies altered levels of key genes involved in redox, inflammation, or pigmentation processes in melanocyte cells in vitiligo. Most published studies have focused on the role of the immune response in non-segmental vitiligo (or vitiligo), which accounts for approximately 90% of clinical forms; segmental vitiligo has been less studied. In their review, Speekkaert et al. emphasize the role of autoimmunity in segmental vitiligo. It is likely that an immune response is triggered against melanocytes carrying the somatic mutation (5,33,27). Indeed, as shown by Yang et al., transcriptomic analysis of lesional skin of segmental vitiligo versus non-segmental vitiligo revealed similar changes in dysregulated immune pathways. The innate immune response is important for disease initiation. Jadeja et al. discuss the role of the endoplasmic reticulum stress-induced unfolded protein response as a bridge between oxidative stress and the development of autoimmunity in vitiligo. Danger signals (DAMPs and PAMPs) along with the role of innate immune cells in the pathogenesis of vitiligo are reviewed by Boniface et al., which are important for the subsequent activation of adaptive T-cell immune responses, leading to melanocyte loss. Indeed, CD8+ T cells infiltrating the skin of patients with vitiligo play a direct role in melanocyte loss through their cytotoxic activity and the release of type 1 cytokines, particularly IFN γ and TNF α (7,19,30).

Recent studies have also described the role of **persistent memory T cells expressing IL-15 receptors, CXCR3, and NKG2D**, and targeting this subset is important for preventing disease progression and maintaining repigmentation after treatment (2,34,8). In this context, Plaza-Rojas and Guevara-Patiño discuss the role of the NKG2D/NKG2D ligand axis, and Willemsen et al. have investigated the relevance of targeting the PD-1/PD-L1 axis in vitiligo. The breakdown of tolerance is a hallmark of autoimmunity, and previous studies have described impaired function and/or number of regulatory T cells in patients (36,33,29,10). In their original article, Mukhatayev et al. investigated the potential of CAR Tregs as a therapeutic strategy in a preclinical mouse model predisposed to the development of vitiligo. The importance of using appropriate in vitro and in vivo preclinical models for mechanistic and translational studies is highlighted in the review by Katz and Harris. Animal models of vitiligo, as a spontaneous disease, are not optimal for fully understanding the complexity of the human disease. In their series, Egbeto et al. described a similar immune profile between canine and human autoimmune pigmentary diseases, suggesting that findings in one model may be relevant to the other. In summary, the important role of autoimmune processes in the pathogenesis of vitiligo is now clearly evident, as exemplified by recent clinical trials evaluating the efficacy of drugs targeting the immune response, such as JAK inhibitors (37,23). Nevertheless, assessing drug efficacy is important for individualized therapeutic management of patients. Yang et al. identified biomarkers of innate and adaptive immune responses associated with a positive response to therapy. It is also important to assess whether new treatments will result in long-lasting repigmentation of vitiligo or whether maintenance therapy will be required to prevent disease recurrence.

CONCLUSIONS.

In this review we summarize recent advances in immunopathology of vitiligo, including statistical, clinical, immunological, biochemical analysis based on etipathogenesis for diseases. There is still much to accomplish for precise etiopathogenesis for vitiligo patients, and additional modalities also

need to be developed and validated. This review may act as a supplement of recent immunology of vitiligo guidelines and expert consensus. Large-scale clinical research based on the phenotype approach is highly warranted in the future.

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